

IoTEdu Core: Automated Intrusion Detection and Response in IoT Environments through Multi-IDS Orchestration

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Abstract. *IoT environments increase the attack surface and challenge incident response. IoTEdu orchestrates multiple IDSs (Suricata, Snort, Zeek) in a unified pipeline with event correlation and automated blocking. Across five attack types (75 runs), it achieves 5.56s average containment, with latency dominated by detection. Results expose a trade-off between signature-based speed and behavior-based context, showing that multi-IDS orchestration improves automated response in dynamic IoT settings.*

1. Introduction

The accelerated growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) has transformed institutional environments, such as universities, hospitals, and critical infrastructures, into ecosystems of high operational complexity. Recent estimates indicate more than 21 billion connected devices globally, with annual growth exceeding 14% [IoT Analytics 2025], integrating sensors, actuators, and embedded systems with heterogeneous capabilities, distinct protocols, and, frequently, limited protection mechanisms [Li et al. 2023, Kim and Lee 2024, Rahman et al. 2023]. This heterogeneity substantially expands the attack surface. IoT devices have been exploited as predominant vectors in distributed denial-of-service campaigns and lateral movement within corporate networks, with evidence that more than 30% of incidents in institutional networks involve low-computational-capacity devices [Alqahtani et al. 2023, Nguyen et al. 2024]. In this scenario, the timely detection and containment of intrusions become central challenges, particularly in educational and hospital networks, where device diversity, limited segmentation, and operational constraints hinder the adoption of traditional security architectures.

Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) are widely used to identify malicious activity in IoT networks. As synthesized in Table 1, the recent literature can be organized into three main fronts: comparative performance evaluations [Waleed et al. 2022, Boukebous et al. 2023, Qutqut et al. 2026], integration with analysis and correlation platforms [Alharbi and Khan 2023, Muhammad et al. 2023], and automated response mechanisms [Katsura et al. 2022, Praptodiyono et al. 2023]. Comparative studies highlight relevant differences in throughput and latency among Snort, Suricata, and Zeek, but remain confined to isolated performance analysis or log generation, without integration across multiple IDS nor effective response mechanisms. Integration-based approaches with external platforms advance by combining multiple IDS in distributed architectures; however, they are limited to event aggregation and visualization, without coupling to mitigation plans. Conversely, solutions

that incorporate automatic blocking demonstrate reduced containment latency, but operate with a single IDS and without correlation across multiple alert sources. Additionally, machine learning-based approaches, such as Ouiazane et al. 2022, enhance detection capability but remain in passive mode, lacking automated response mechanisms.

As a result, a key limitation in the state of the art remains: no existing approach simultaneously integrates heterogeneous multi-IDS orchestration, real-time event correlation, and automated dynamic blocking. This gap leads to longer exposure windows, redundant alerts, and less informed mitigation decisions, particularly in dynamic IoT environments.

Table 1. IDS-based approaches in IoT environments. Detection: signature, anomaly, or hybrid. Architecture: standalone or distributed. Composition: homogeneous (single IDS) or heterogeneous (multiple IDSs). Operation: detection only or detection with automated response.

Reference	IDS	Detection	Architecture	Composition	Operation
[Qutqut et al. 2026]	Snort, Suricata	Signature	Standalone	Heterogeneous	Detection
[Katsura et al. 2022]	Snort 2.9.9	Signature	Distributed	Homogeneous	Detection + Response
[Praptodiyono et al. 2023]	Suricata	Signature	Distributed	Homogeneous	Detection + Response
[Boukebous et al. 2023]	Snort2, Snort3, Suricata	Signature	Standalone	Heterogeneous	Detection
[Muhammad et al. 2023]	Zeek, Slips	Anomaly	Distributed	Heterogeneous	Detection
[Waleed et al. 2022]	Snort, Suricata, Zeek	Hybrid	Standalone	Heterogeneous	Detection + Response
[Ouiazane et al. 2022]	Suricata (SNIDS)	Hybrid	Distributed	Homogeneous	Detection
[Alharbi and Khan 2023]	Suricata, Zeek, Slips	Hybrid	Distributed	Heterogeneous	Detection
IoTEdu Core This work	Snort, Suricata, Zeek	Hybrid	Distributed	Heterogeneous	Detection + Response

To address this gap, this work presents IoTEdu Core, which is part of the IoTEdu project¹, an automated detection and response platform based on the orchestration of multiple heterogeneous IDS. The solution integrates Suricata, Snort, and Zeek into a unified monitoring pipeline, correlates events across different sources, and automatically triggers countermeasures through the pfSense firewall, reducing the interval between detection and containment. Evaluated across 75 runs distributed over five attack types, the platform achieves a mean containment time of 5.56,s, with latency dominated by the detection mechanisms rather than by the central orchestration processing.

The main contributions of this work are: (i) a heterogeneous multi-IDS orchestration architecture with event correlation and automated response tailored to institutional IoT environments; (ii) the practical integration of Suricata, Snort, and Zeek into a unified detection and mitigation pipeline, combined with dynamic blocking through pfSense, demonstrating the feasibility of containment within a few seconds under realistic conditions; and (iii) an experimental characterization of the trade-off between response speed, typically associated with signature-based detection, and contextual depth, commonly provided by behavioral analysis, with direct implications for the design of automated defense systems in dynamic IoT environments.

2. Architecture and Instance

IoTEdu Core² is a web platform that enables the management (i.e., registration, control, and monitoring) of IoT devices in institutional networks to track and respond to (manu-

¹<https://gt-iotedu.github.io>

²https://github.com/GT-IoTEdu/sbrc2026_sf_api

ally or automatically) security events detected by multiple IDSs. For instance, consider the following operational scenario. A professor registers an experimental IoT sensor. From that point on, the device’s traffic is monitored and logs are consequently generated. Upon identifying events classified as high or critical severity, the system triggers device blocking and notifies the professor.

The solution integrates detection mechanisms with network services and security appliances, including firewalls and dynamic network configuration services, such as DHCP, enabling not only the identification of malicious behaviors, but also the coordinated enforcement of access control policies and incident containment at the infrastructure level. Furthermore, the platform enables the application of context-aware security policies based on the profile, behavior, and operational context of IoT devices.

Figure 1 presents the solution’s architecture, organized into three main components arranged in layers. At the base lies the most challenging and domain-specific component, referred to as *Network Management Services*. Within it, the *Security Probe* module is currently under development and is left for future work. The *Scanners* module, implemented by instances of *Suricata*³, *Snort*⁴, and *Zeek*⁵, monitors network traffic and generates security logs from suspicious activities. The *Firewalls* module, instantiated by *pfSense*⁶, automatically enforces blocking rules based on API decisions, enabling incident containment at the infrastructure level.

Figure 1. System architecture.

The intermediate component, *Backend*, receives records through the *API* module, which centralizes collection, performs normalization across different formats, correlates events from multiple sources, and classifies them according to their severity. The persistent storage of devices, users, events, and access policies is handled by the *Data Storage* module, implemented by a *MySQL*⁷ database management system.

³<https://suricata.io/>

⁴<https://www.snort.org/>

⁵<https://zeek.org/>

⁶<https://www.pfsense.org/>

⁷<https://www.mysql.com/>

All executed actions and observed events are persisted and made available by the third and final component, `Frontend`. Within it, the `Web Application` module is used for monitoring and auditing purposes by users, who are organized into three access levels. The superuser defines global parameters, institutional networks, and access policies. Administrators manage devices and approvals within their respective networks. Users register IoT devices.

3. Evaluation

We conducted an experimental evaluation to quantify latency in the IoTedu Core processes, organized into two stages. In the first, we focused on processes related to the `Network Management Services` component and, in the second, on the `Frontend`. The methodology and results of each stage are presented below.

3.1. Network Management Services Latency

Figure 2 and Table 2 present, respectively, the experimental environment and the parameters used in the first stage of the evaluation, with a focus on `Network Management Services`. The topology consists of three virtual machines and a local application on the host, isolating the functions of attack generation, network monitoring, and control. All attack traffic is directed to the `enp0s3` interface, used as the observation and capture point of the experimental environment. A dedicated script performs continuous log reading and real-time event forwarding via *Server-Sent Events* (SSE).

Figure 2. Experimental setup for Network Management Services evaluation.

The evaluated metric is the latency measured for the execution of the main stages of the security incident detection and response process: (i) *Detection Start*, which corresponds to the time between the beginning of the attack and the generation of the first alert by the IDS; (ii) *Detection–Blocking*, representing the elapsed time between alert generation and the effective enforcement of the blocking rule in *pfSense*; (iii) *Start–Failure*, which indicates the total exposure time of the system, defined as the interval between the beginning of the attack and its complete interruption or containment; and (iv) *API Processing*, which measures the response time of the IoTedu Core API in handling events received via SSE. Table 3 presents the mean and standard deviation, in seconds, of the

Table 2. Network management services evaluation parameters.

Category	#	Specification
Host	1	Notebook, Oracle VirtualBox 7.1.12, Windows 11 Pro 64-bit, Intel Core i7-1185G7 (1.80 GHz base / 3.00 GHz boost), 32 GB RAM
Attacker VM	1	Linux Mint 22.3 (Zena), Ubuntu 24.04 (Noble) x86_64 base, kernel 6.14.0-37-generic, 1 vCPU, 2 GB RAM, Intel 82540EM (enp0s3)
Monitoring VM	1	Ubuntu 24.04 (Noble) x86_64, kernel 6.17.0-14-generic, 1 vCPU, 2 GB RAM, Intel 82540EM (enp0s3)
Firewall VM	1	pfSense 2.8.1-RELEASE, FreeBSD 15.0-CURRENT, 4 vCPUs, 8 GB RAM, Intel 82540EM (UEFI)
IoTEdu Core	1	API running locally on the host
Evaluated IDSs	3	Suricata, Snort, Zeek
Attack Scenarios	5	HTTP Flood, ICMP Flood, DNS Tunneling, SSH Brute Force, SQL Injection
Runs	5	per IDS per attack, totaling 15 runs per attack type and 75 runs overall
Stages	4	Detection Start, Detection–Blocking, Start–Failure, API Processing

Table 3. Latency of Operation by IDS (mean \pm std. dev. after 5 runs).

Scanner	Start of Detection	Detection-Blocking	Start-Fail	API processing
Snort	1.450 \pm 0.596	1.417 \pm 0.295	4.732 \pm 1.385	0.363 \pm 0.121
Suricata	0.881 \pm 0.414	0.616 \pm 0.210	3.160 \pm 0.469	0.543 \pm 0.187
Zeek	3.208 \pm 1.165	3.595 \pm 2.466	8.808 \pm 3.202	0.382 \pm 0.190
Global	1.847 \pm 1.267	1.876 \pm 1.903	5.567 \pm 3.124	0.430 \pm 0.185

latency of the four stages of the process for each IDS individually and grouped globally. The values aggregate all five repetitions of all five attacks.

We highlight three main observations. First, the analysis of standard deviation provides evidence of measurement consistency, validating the methodology provided that the scope aspects are taken into account. In our environment, Suricata presented the best performance in terms of latency, as it achieved the lowest times across all stages, along with the lowest standard deviation, indicating consistency and better predictability.

Finally, the overall system latency is predominantly determined by the detection and alert generation stages, rather than by the central API processing, indicating that our implementation adds little overhead to the process. The *API Processing* stage exhibits low mean and reduced variability, indicating stable behavior and a marginal contribution to the total response time. In contrast, the *Detection Start*, *Detection–Blocking*, and, most notably, *Start–Failure* stages display greater dispersion, suggesting that the overall system variability is predominantly determined by the performance of the IDSs and by the speed at which each mechanism transforms observations into actionable alerts.

Figure 3 shows a heat map of the average latency of the *Start–Failure* stage aggregated by evaluated IDS (rows) and by attack scenario (column). In nearly all scenarios,

Suricata presented the lowest average times, followed by Snort, while Zeek presented the highest values. This result is consistent with the nature of the tools: Snort and Suricata are predominantly signature-oriented, favoring rapid response to known patterns, whereas Zeek relies more heavily on behavioral analysis, event correlation, and state maintenance. This difference becomes particularly evident in the *SQL Injection* attack, in which Zeek tends to depend on the analysis of multiple application-layer records before producing an actionable alert, while Snort and Suricata can react directly to malicious patterns in the HTTP payload. For *HTTP Flood* and *ICMP Flood*, the difference is also consistent with the fact that Snort and Suricata apply thresholds directly over packets or requests, whereas Zeek tends to react to the aggregated traffic behavior.

Figure 3. Heat map - IDS vs Type of Attack (Start-Fail).

The interpretation of the results requires consideration of the structural differences between the detection mechanisms. Although all three IDSs were configured to cover the same experimental scenarios, their approaches are not methodologically equivalent. Snort and Suricata adopt signature-based detection, with direct pattern matching over packets or flows, whereas Zeek employs event-driven scripts, incorporating behavioral correlation, temporal analysis, and state maintenance. It is important to note that we used the default configuration of each tool. As a consequence, Snort and Suricata tend to react more rapidly to known patterns, while Zeek depends, in several cases, on the accumulation of context before producing an actionable alert. Future work includes the incorporation of signature-based detection in Zeek, through additional (i.e., non-default) resources, and the expansion of the rule set to cover a larger number of attacks.

This distinction becomes evident across the different attack types. In *SQL Injection*, Snort and Suricata detect sequences directly in the HTTP payload, whereas Zeek analyzes events such as `http_request`, performs URI normalization, and may require multiple occurrences within a time window. In SSH brute-force attacks, Snort and Suricata employ mechanisms such as `detection_filter` and `threshold`, while Zeek maintains counters in state structures from events such as `ssh_capabilities` and `ssh_auth_attempted`. Analogously, in *HTTP Flood*, *ICMP Flood*, and *DNS Tunneling*, Snort and Suricata operate with thresholds and direct signatures, whereas Zeek relies on aggregated analysis and events such as `dns_request` and entries in `conn.log`.

These differences indicate that Snort and Suricata exhibit structural equivalence, whereas Zeek maintains predominantly functional equivalence. This contrast explains both the differences observed in detection times and the higher level of contextualization

provided by Zeek alerts, evidencing a *trade-off* between response speed and depth.

3.2. Frontend Latency

To evaluate latency from the end-user perspective via the Web interface, *Selenium* was used to execute tasks on the platform across the three core operations it supports: IoT device registration, access grant, and manual blocking by the administrator. The tests simulate the complete operational flow: 16 devices are registered on the platform by a regular user, followed by manual grant and blocking performed by the administrator. The response time of each operation is measured as the interval between the timestamp of the button click that triggers the action and the timestamp of the database write, at which point the API has already completed processing and the response has been received by the client. Each operation was executed 32 times, totaling 96 runs for the three operations. Table 4 summarizes the results obtained. Detailed data can be found in Appendix A.

Table 4. Web Application Response Times (seconds).

Operation	Mean \pm Std. Dev.	Interval (s)
Blocking	0.693 \pm 0.297	0.117–1.192
Registration	0.241 \pm 0.134	0.012–0.504
Grant	0.361 \pm 0.196	0.007–0.709

The high standard deviation observed ($\approx 50\%$) stems from the nature of Selenium-based automation, which operates at the graphical interface layer and is subject to variabilities inherent to the execution environment, such as system resource contention, browser rendering latency, variations in application response time under different cache conditions, and fluctuations in asynchronous JavaScript event execution. These factors are characteristic of approaches that emulate real user interactions and confer greater realism to the measurements, albeit at the cost of increased statistical dispersion. These results therefore reinforce the methodological decision to organize the evaluation into two stages, isolating the analysis of critical components from interface-layer variability.

The results evidence three clearly distinct behaviors across the operations. The *blocking* operation is the most time-consuming, which was expected given its greater processing complexity among the analyzed operations: in addition to updating the database, it triggers the IoTEdu Core API to enforce a containment rule via *pfSense*. Following this rationale, the *registration* operation presents the shortest duration, while *grant* occupies an intermediate position.

4. Availability and Demonstration Plan

To support validation, reproducibility, and reuse, the IoTEdu Core source code is publicly available on GitHub². The repository enables the deployment of the complete detection and response pipeline, including integration with multiple IDSs, event correlation, and automated mitigation mechanisms, in virtualized and reproducible environments.

The demonstration uses commodity hardware with virtual machines for attack generation, network monitoring, and control, evidencing the complete system flow from real-time monitoring and alert generation by multiple IDSs (Suricata, Snort, and Zeek)

to centralized correlation by the IoTEdu API and automatic blocking via *pfSense*. A web interface supports device, network, and alert management, demonstrating end-to-end integration between detection and network infrastructure, with dynamic rule installation, traceability, and multi-IDS correlation in realistic IoT scenarios.

5. Conclusion and Future Work

This work presented IoTEdu Core, an automated detection and response platform for IoT environments based on the orchestration of multiple IDSs, event correlation, and dynamic blocking at the network infrastructure level. The integration of Suricata, Snort, and Zeek into a unified pipeline enables reducing the interval between detection and containment.

The evaluation showed an average response time of 5.56s, with latency dominated by detection rather than the API. Suricata achieved the lowest latency, while Zeek provided richer contextualization, highlighting the trade-off between response speed and analytical depth. These results confirm the viability of multi-IDS orchestration for automated response in IoT environments.

As future work, the following directions stand out: (i) the extension of Zeek with signature-based detection support, enabling methodologically equivalent comparisons among IDSs; (ii) the use of machine learning models for alert prioritization and filtering; (iii) the enhancement of multi-source and temporal correlation; (iv) the optimization of the detection pipeline and the detection–action cycle, with a focus on reducing containment latency; and (v) validation in real-world environments, including direct comparisons with non-orchestrated architectures.

References

- Alharbi, S. and Khan, A. (2023). Ensemble defense system: A hybrid ids approach for effective cyber threat detection. In *2023 33rd International Telecommunication Networks and Applications Conference*, pages 267–270.
- Alqahtani, S. et al. (2023). Cybersecurity threats in iot environments: Recent advances and challenges. *Journal of Network and Computer Applications*.
- Boukebous, A. A. E., Fettache, M. I., Bendiab, G., and Shiaeles, S. (2023). A comparative analysis of snort 3 and suricata. In *2023 IEEE IAS Global Conference on Emerging Technologies (GlobConET)*, pages 1–6.
- IoT Analytics (2025). State of iot 2025: Number of connected iot devices growing 13% to 21.1 billion globally. Accessed: 2026.
- Katsura, Y., Sakarin, P., Yamai, N., Kimiyama, H., and Visoottiviseth, V. (2022). Quick blocking operation of firewall system cooperating with ids and sdn. In *2022 24th ICACT*, pages 393–398.
- Kim, J. and Lee, H. (2024). Recent advances in iot architectures and applications: A comprehensive survey. *Future Generation Computer Systems*.
- Li, S., Xu, L. D., and Zhao, S. (2023). Security challenges and opportunities in internet of things: A survey. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*.
- Muhammad, A. R., Sukarno, P., and Wardana, A. A. (2023). Integrated security information and event management (siem) with intrusion detection system (ids) for live

analysis based on machine learning. *Procedia Computer Science*, 217:1406–1415. ISM 2022.

Nguyen, T. et al. (2024). Security and privacy challenges in iot-based smart environments. *Computer Networks*.

Ouiazzane, S., Addou, M., and Barramou, F. (2022). A suricata and machine learning based hybrid network intrusion detection system. In Maleh, Y., Alazab, M., Gherabi, N., Tawalbeh, L., and Abd El-Latif, A. A., editors, *Advances in Information, Communication and Cybersecurity*, pages 474–485, Cham. Springer International Publishing.

Praptodiyono, S., Firmansyah, T., Anwar, M. H., Wicaksana, C. A., Pramudyo, A. S., and Al-Allawee, A. (2023). Development of hybrid intrusion detection system based on suricata with pfsense method for high reduction of ddos attacks on ipv6 networks. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 5(9 (125)):75–84.

Qutqut, M. H., Ahmed, A., Taqi, M. K., Abimanyu, J., Ajes, E. T., and Alhaj, F. (2026). A comparative evaluation of snort and suricata for detecting data exfiltration tunnels in cloud environments. *Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy*, 6(1).

Rahman, M. et al. (2023). Edge computing for iot: Security and scalability challenges. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*.

Waleed, A., Jamali, A. F., and Masood, A. (2022). Which open-source ids? snort, suricata or zeek. *Computer Networks*, 213:109116.

A. Automated Tests with Selenium

Performance tests were carried out using the *Selenium* tool, automating the three main operations of the platform: *registration*, *blocking*, and *access grant*. Each of the two evaluators independently executed 16 repetitions per operation, totaling 32 runs per operation and 96 response time records in the consolidated dataset.

A.1. Response Times

Table 5 presents the consolidated descriptive statistics for each operation, considering the mean, standard deviation, and minimum and maximum values of the collected times.

Table 5. Statistical summary of response times per operation

Operation	Number of tests	Mean (s)	Standard Deviation (s)	Min. – Max. (s)
Blocking	32	0.693	0.297	0.117 – 1.192
Registration	32	0.241	0.134	0.012 – 0.504
Grant	32	0.361	0.196	0.007 – 0.709

The *blocking* operation presented the highest mean response time (0.693 s), as well as the greatest variability (standard deviation of 0.297 s), indicating that its processing is more costly and less predictable across runs. The *registration* operation was consistently the fastest, with a mean of 0.241 s and the lowest standard deviation (0.134 s), suggesting more stable behavior. *Grant* occupied an intermediate position, with a mean of 0.361 s and a standard deviation of 0.196 s.

Figure 4. Median response time per operation.

Figure 5. Platform performance trend (consolidated average per sequential execution)

A.2. Performance Trend Across Sequential Runs

The analysis of the performance trend across sequential runs (Figure 6) revealed a progressive decrease in response times as the runs advance. This behavior is characteristic of application warm-up effects and cache mechanisms, which reduce the loading time of previously accessed resources. At the 16th run, all operations converged to values close to 0.05 s, regardless of initial times.

A.3. Variability and Measurement Consistency

The consolidated median response times, presented in Appendix 4, confirmed the mean results: 0.651 s for *blocking*, 0.225 s for *registration*, and 0.408 s for *grant*. The proximity between mean and median across all operations indicates relatively symmetric distributions, without significant distortions caused by outliers.

Regarding standard deviation, illustrated in Appendix 5, *blocking* recorded the greatest variation (0.297 s), followed by *grant* (0.196 s) and *registration* (0.134 s). These

Figure 6. Platform performance trend (consolidated average per sequential execution)

values are consistent with the complexity of each operation: *blocking* involves more processing steps and is therefore more susceptible to performance fluctuations.

Overall, the response times obtained fall within acceptable limits for web systems, given that all operations were completed in under 1.2 s even in the worst observed case. The decreasing behavior across sequential runs suggests that, under continuous use, the platform tends to operate with latencies significantly lower than those measured in the first cold runs.